

CHARACTERIZATION OF NANOFIBERS FOR TISSUE ENGINEERING: CHEMICAL MAPPING BY CONFOCAL RAMAN MICROSCOPY

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As a method of nanofiber characterization, Raman spectroscopy typically has been used in combination with imaging by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) [12-19], transmission electron microscopy (TEM) [13, 16, 20-23], x-ray diffraction (XRD) [13] or atomic force microscopy (AFM) [9]. Such studies either rely on sample homogeneity when the spectral signature is examined [12-17], or use the non-chemical properties of different fiber components, such as density [23] or surface roughness [9], to determine their spatial distribution.

In this review, we concentrate on applications of confocal Raman microscopy to analyze the **structure** of inhomogeneous nanofibers, consisting of different types of polymers, which is increasingly popular for tissue engineering applications. In those cases, often the nanoscale features are resolved by means of oversampling and extensive data processing, including Classical Least Squares (CLS) decomposition and Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) techniques. Confocal Raman microscopy allows direct chemical detection of various polymers, but the resolution of this technique tends to exceed the nanofiber thickness. As a result, just mapping the nanofibers using the CRM is insufficient, and further data processing (chemometrics) is required to extract the information about the component distribution within nanofibers [31-32].

Raman spectroscopy is a highly effective tool for identification of a variety of materials (Camposeo et al., 2016; Colthup, 2012). This technique relies on the inelastic scattering of light by molecules, which yields information about their vibrational modes, and structural and electronic properties. Raman spectroscopy is fast and non-destructive, offering high sensitivity in the detection of different species (Eesley, 2013). It can be integrated with advanced optical microscopy hardware, such as optical fibers, miniaturized lasers and other photonic devices to improve its diagnostic performance (Ferrari et al., 2013; Guieu et al., 2008; De Luca et al., 2008). It allows chemical analysis by optical means, without reagents, staining, or sample preparation. As a result, it has been used in a wide variety of applications, such as investigation of biocompatible polymers (Taddei et al., 2001) and carbon-based materials, including carbon nanotubes (Bokobza et al., 2013; Pawlyta et al., 2015; Deldicque et al., 2016).

Table 2. The advantages and disadvantages of Confocal Raman Scanning for composite nanofiber characterization.

Advantages of Raman:
Will work when the core and shell polymers are of the of similar density
Will work when the core and shell polymers have very similar hydrophobicity
Does not require vacuum - the samples can be analyzed with cells seeded on them

Disadvantages of Raman

The resolution is limited to the fraction of the beam size, which is on the order of hundreds of nanometers

Nanofiber characterization is crucial to confirm and fine tune various nanofiber properties. It can be performed by different techniques, depending on the parameters that have to be determined. In most cases, a combination of techniques is used to find all required nanofiber properties. We discussed various applications where scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), x-ray diffraction (XRD) and confocal Raman microscopy (CRM).

CRM is of particular interest, since it can be used for 3D mapping of chemical composition of multi-component nanofibers, by simultaneously acquiring both spectral and spatial information about the sample. Such mapping is usually performed on microscopic scale; however, nanoscale resolution can be achieved by oversampling and data processing (for example, using SVD). In many cases, this is the preferred way to confirm the spatial distribution of different chemical components within multi-component nanofibers, which is particularly important for nanofiber scaffolds used in bioengineering for functional support of growing tissues.